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Impact of Pastoral Counselling in Christ Apostolic Church (C.A.C) Oke-Anu in Ilorin Metropolis

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Abstract

Pastoral counselling uniquely merges spiritual guidance with psychological support to address intricate family dynamics. It helps to synergies pastoral care and family counselling, integrating faith and therapy to heal emotions and enrich familial bonds. The church is a spiritual space where people meet for the purpose of worship. However, the church has been seen not only as a place of worship but also a place for spiritual healing which finds expression in prayer, psalmody, fasting and as well the talk-therapy by proffering solutions to family related issues. The paper therefore examines the impact of pastoral counselling in Christ Apostolic Church (C.A.C) Oke-Anu in Ilorin Metropolis. Data were harvested through interviews from pastors and members of the congregation, historical and descriptive methods were adopted as secondary sources. It was discovered that there is huge impacts of pastoral counselling on families in the church and through various pastoral engagements in the light of talk therapy many families have been saved at the verge of divorce and marital failure. It also shows that interactions between pastors and members have helped to identify problems and provide solutions in the church and homes. The paper concluded that talk therapy is a viable tool to reduce the issue of conflict in homes and church as seen in C.A.C Oke-Anu, Ilorin. Therefore, the study recommended that the pastoral counselling should be embraced by all pastors and also pastors should be well-informed and trained about ethics of counselling.

Keywords: Christ Apostolic Church Oke-Anu, Family Counselling, Spiritual Therapy Pastoral Counselling, Ilorin Metropolis

Introduction

One of the common imprints about Christ Apostolic Church is the spontaneous saying of prayers in their gatherings and prayers have always been the basis of their regular meetings. Due to their prayer life, it is given a nomenclature known as "praying church", to indicate a church that is known for no other business than prayer. The place of the church in keeping the prayer life of members which can be seen as its legacy and heritage cannot be contested but rather view with an eagle eye as a panacea to spiritual and physical challenges. At the centre of

spirituality and physicality lies the root of counselling as another diversified medium to combat against spiritual and physical maladies. Aldridge (2014) cited *Royal College of Psychiatrists'* on counselling that counselling is a general term for exploring emotional problems by talking them through with a trained counsellor or therapist. The view of Aldridge is aptly to the current situation in Christ Apostolic Church where Pastors are not only concerned about praying for deliverance but by incorporating talk session into solving spiritual problems, and problems caused as a result of contraction in social relations.

Pastoral counselling involves the steps –proactive and active steps taken to combat against and integrate psychological, family and spiritual differences in the life of congregants through the use of scriptural passages that are relevant and appropriate to the situation of the counselees. Pastoral counselling involves talking with people one-on-one, in relationships, and in families to help them better understand emotional and religious challenges and to find solutions utilizing both religious and secular resources (Encyclopedia.com, n.d.). Counselling on its own is a scope that cannot be limited to faith-based institution such as Christianity but rather by extension is a conscious and unconscious practice in the traditional African society. At the family level, counselling can be seen as an advice, while in the religious level (African Religion), it can be viewed as consultation. At an administrative level, counselling can be seen as directives, instructions, seminars, workshop amongst others. However, in the medical sphere, it can be viewed as a healing measure where the therapist converse with the counselee to acquire the information needed in order to proffer the adequate solution needed.

The essence of counselling has necessitated the development of counselling as a course in tertiary institutions. In secondary schools, the guidance and counselling unit is put in place with a professional counsellor who guides the efforts and choice of learners to fruition. Hence, counselling is not limited to a particular sector rather it is an encompassing act in every human endeavours with variance in the level of expertise. It is no gainsay to accentuate that the level of counselling in Christ Apostolic Church Oke-Anu is of a great commendation to the growth and application of counselling to solving disputes in the church and families thus providing vitality for the sustainability of the family and the church at large thereby creating a safe society where spirituality and physicality converse to ameliorate man's challenges.

The thrust of this paper is to reveal the impacts of pastoral counselling in Christ Apostolic Church (C.A.C) Oke-Anu. The paper is thus subdivided into; the concept of pastoral counselling forms of pastoral counselling, brief history of Christ Apostolic Church Oke-Anu in Ilorin, District Coordinating Council (DCC) headquarters, Ilorin, strategies adopted for pastoral counselling in C.A.C Oke-Anu, impact of pastoral counselling on the Church and conclusion.

The Concept of Pastoral Counselling

The term "Pastoral Counselling" can be derived from two independent words –Pastoral from Pastor and Counselling from Counsel. A Pastor is an oracle of God who teaches and preaches the good news and oversees the Church. The role of the Pastor is usually narrowed to the role of a shepherd. The word translated "Pastors" here is the Greek word *Poimen*, meaning "a herdsman, especially a shepherd" (Carter, n.d.). Durojaiye (1987) opines that counselling involves the development of interaction through the relationship between a trained therapist

(counsellor) and a troubled person in a perceived temporary state of indecision, confusion, malfunction, habit disorder, distress or despair. Akinade (2012) corroborated Durojaiye's view on counselling. He defined counselling as a number of procedures used in assisting an individual in solving problems which arise in various aspects of a counselee's life.

The significant similarity between the definitions of Durojaiye and Akinade is the formative factor that led to counselling – a problem. Hansen, Stevic, and Warner (1982) affirmed that the purpose of counselling is to provide for the individual functions in a social context and not in isolation. To understand the position of Hansen et al, McLeod (2007) buttressed further that counselling is an activity which takes place when someone who is troubled invites and allows another person to enter into a particular relationship with them. Hence, the "social context" which Hansen portrayed found expression in the "invitation into a relationship" of McLeod. This implies that counselling as act is not or cannot be achieved in isolation rather in a social context where relationship is ignited.

Pastoral Counselling is the "relationship or talk relationship" established between a counsellor, who is a pastor or uses pastoral methods and approach such as using biblical quotations, references, pastoral care and a counselee, who is either a member of the congregation or an outsider. McLeod (2007) cited Vance and Volsky (1962) that counselling deals with so-called individuals whose problems are developmental in nature. It can be deduced that problems are of stages and the need to approach these diversities made counselling to continue to be relevant. Murry (2005) cited Clinbell that Pastoral Counselling as "the application of a range of healing techniques to assist individuals in handling their issues and crises more fully and, as a result, experiencing healing of their brokenness".

The human society has been characterized with several issues which often lead to misunderstanding and conflict, thus, the need to engage the existential realities through a talk therapy is important. The church space is not indispensable since it is a society where people relate, relationship is established and communication is enhanced. The Pastor is one who is saddled with the responsibilities to feed God's people with His word.

In the biblical accounts, pastoral counselling is made evident from both testaments. In the Old Testament there are several allusions to pastoral counselling such as Jethro counselled Moses (Exo. 18:17-23), Isaiah counselled Hezekiah (2 Kgs 19), Rebecca counselled Jacob (Gen. 27:57), Samuel ministry also provides an insight to pastoral counselling. Furthermore, in the New Testament pastoral counselling was evidence through Jesus' teachings and ministry, and in several Pauline epistles such as Rom. 12:15 and 1 Thess. 2:11-12. Pastoral counselling is the conscious and intentional use of divine provisions through the scriptural passages to heal, bring calmness and proffer solutions to problems. Asamoah opines that "Pastoral counselling is a psychotherapeutic approach to counselling that employs biblically spiritual and ethical principles to decode and address client problems that may be of emotional, spiritual, psychological, physical and material or socio-cultural nature".

Counselling is an enlightened process whereby counsellors help counsees by facilitating growth and positive adjustment through self-understanding (Akinade, 2012). One of the ways to be emancipated is through self-understanding. It is pertinent for the counsees to understand the situation not only through their views but through the views of the counsellor.

Gail (2010) remarks that counselling developed from the psychoanalytic theory of Sigmund Freud and was first introduced as such to Britain in the 1950s via the National Marriage Guidance Council, now called "Relate". Pastoral counselling started as a separate discipline in the North America as far back as the 12th century (Wikipedia, n.d.). GoodTherapy (2021) writes:

Ministers of all religions usually offer counselling to members of their religious communities. For support, direction, and solutions relating to *mental* health difficulties, people have long looked to religious leaders. Pastoral counselling was developed with the understanding that, while this form of support is beneficial, other problems can call for a higher calibre of assistance.

From the foregoing, pastoral counselling emerged to provide support, direction and solutions to members with mental health and marital challenges. Counselling is timeless. It is not time framed or bound. It can be planned and unplanned. Thus, a pastor's word(s) of advice at any time and at any given place can also be regarded as pastoral counselling. McLeod (2007) corroborated this view by saying that counselling can be a brief conversation of only a few minutes, within a "window of opportunity" that arises during involvement in other helping, caring or clinical activities. Pastoral counselling can also be called "divine counselling" since pastors are looked upon as God's representative to His people.

Forms of Pastoral Counselling

Pastoral counselling has engaged both spiritual and physical issues emerging within the faith-based i.e the church through teaching, sermonizing and instructing an individual or group of individuals. Pastoral counselling can be **individual and group** in nature. Akinade (2012) cited McLeod that an **individual counselling** is a professional assistance in which the counsellor works on a one-to-one basis with the clients to help them resolve their mental and social problems. It connotes a session whereby the counsellor has a direct "talk" with the counselee without hindrance. This is one of the commonest ways used in churches today to address families intricate matters arising in the spiritual domains.

The need for individual counselling is to afford and assure the confidentiality of the counselee who wants to divulge the truth behind the identified problems. In Nigerian Churches, ministers like Pastor E.A. Adeboye, Pastor W.F. Kumuyi amongst others, allow their wives to handle some individual counselling among members and those who are non-members but come for counselling. It is pertinent to say that individual counselling can also be necessitated based on the trust of the assumed counsellor. This finds expression in the fixed mindset of some counselees who conceived that a problem can be fully addressed by a "particular" pastor, or so to say that one can only abide by what such individual counsellor has to say about the problem. Pastoral Counselling entails sessions with individuals such as family, friends, couples and other close relatives and friends may be included in pastoral therapy. Pastoral counsellors can provide both family and couple counselling; but, in some instances, they may concentrate primarily on these relationships (Zencare, n.d.). Individual counselling is a concentrated and narrow-centred approach that is believed to address a particular counselee or specific individual at a given time. In this situation, the counsellor only listens to a particular counselee and suggests a panacea that can alleviate the problem. Patterson (1971) asserted that counselling

is a relationship in which the counsellor must understand the client. Thus, the counsellor needs to comprehend the counselee's situation to proffer a suitable solution.

Group counselling implies the collectiveness, commonness, and generality of counsellor to counsel diverse counsees with the same or similar problems. Akinade (2012) opined that a group counselling is an interpersonal process in which a professionally trained counsellor helps more than one person or individuals who are having similar problems. He went further to assert that it is a process of using group interaction to facilitate the understanding and self-acceptance of individuals in the group. Group counselling is also a common form of pastoral counselling found mostly among Nigerian Church leaders. Pastors tend to collate and address issues with specific similarities to proffer a solution that can be applied to the problem. Counselling Centre of the University of Illinois (n.d.) writes:

Group counselling is a form of psychotherapy that usually involves four to ten participants and one or two group therapists. Most groups meet regularly at the same time for one to two hours. During that time, the members of the group discuss the issues that are concerning them and offer each other support and feedback. Interpersonal interaction is highly valued and encouraged.

From the definition above, group counselling involves a range of number of counsellors and counsees within a particular range of time for a specific purpose. In other to settle family disputes, both individual and group counselling may be adopted. It is individual when the pastor seeks the audience of either the husband or wife, but, it becomes a group counselling when the spouses are on seat for the session.

Brief History of Christ Apostolic Church, Oke-Anu, DCC Headquarters, Ilorin

Generally, the history of Christ Apostolic Church in Ilorin metropolis can be traced back to July 1947 by the leading of the Holy Spirit when one Prophet P. A. Olagbami came from Offa to Ilorin for a revival programme. The church started in a very small way in the house of one Elder Ikuforiji, the acting chief sanitary, who was then staying at Opo-Maaluu quarters. They started with morning and evening prayer meetings. People brought their different problems and challenges to God like diseases, barrenness, and demonic attacks etc., and there were records of supernatural interventions in answer to prayers (Abolaji, 2022).

However, the history of Christ Apostolic Church Oke-Anu began in the year 1978 after a great revival service held by a group of other Christ Apostolic Church (C.A.C.) members around Ilorin province in the same year. Its first service was held by Evangelist R.A. Fasoyin and Pastor Michael Agbedde from Oke-Isegun (Mountain of Victory) and other fathers from Sabo-Oke and Agbo-Oba areas on August 14, 1978 where about forty-three people attended the service exclusive the children and representatives from other C.A.C branches in Ilorin (C.A.C Oke-Anu, 2023).

The revival was birthed from a vision given to the then Pastor –Pastor Michael Agbedde (late), who also chaired the revival team. He was given a vision by the Lord that he should start another branch of the C.A.C. around Gaa-Akanbi area of Ilorin to make it the fourth branch within the major part of the town. The revival service itself, led by Prophet- Evangelist Michael O. Adio was so mighty, crucial and effective that it made awareness to C.A.C. members living

around the area. It also gradually brought about the attendance of other non-C.A.C members as well. Initially, service was held at a land space which was borrowed from one of the church member –Elder D.A. Dada who also laboured hard in aiding the church to purchase and acquire a four plot of land –where the church is currently situated (C.A.C Oke-Anu, 2023).

C.A.C. Oke-Anu continued to grow through the help of the Lord and through prayers, commitments and dedication from members and other faithful. It became a District in 1993 during the tenure of Pastor Akinyele. December 2008, under the leadership of Pastor Adeolu Bokode it aroused the status of a Zonal Headquarter, then in the year 2015 the church became a Districts Coordinating Council (DCC). C.A.C. Oke-Anu now has many branches such as C.A.C. Oke-Ibukun, C.A.C. Temidire, C.A.C. Oke-irapada in Asa-dam area of Ilorin, C.A.C. Tanke-Iledu, C.A.C. Chapel of Mercy (English Assembly), C.A.C. Oke-anu II (in Amoyo area Ilorin), C.A.C. Oke-anu III (Atere/Agah area), with four among them rising to District levels (C.A.C Oke-Anu, 2023).

Strategies Adopted for Pastoral Counselling in CAC Oke-Anu

Pastoral counselling in C.A.C Oke-Anu is paramount and it has been viewed as an important tool for church growth and transformation since the inception of the Church (Pastor Jaiyeola, personal communication, September 17, 2023). Dicks (1963) seeks to make a distinction between the approaches of the psychologist and of the pastor. He went to further to states:

Psychology studies the behaviour of people, whereas religion provides the hope for these same people regardless of their behaviour. Psychology focuses upon human relationships as they are while religion inspires and motivates people to change and improve their condition. Supported by psychology and religion the pastor moves into the arena of relationships and becomes an active participant.

From the excerpt above, Dicks provides a distinction between the approaches of the psychologist and of the pastor in a precise summary using behaviour of people and hope of people to explain the meaning of pastoral counselling. Thus, it is important to state that Christ Apostolic Church Oke-Anu resonate Dicks views on Pastor’s approach in counselling. The church counselling unit is headed by the curate pastor, Pastor T.O. Ogunleye. The unit meets regularly to ensure love and unity are maintained and restored in the church. The normal protocol before engaging the services of the unit is to be scheduled after proper dissemination of information either through verbal communication or a counselling leaflet that is given to the counselee which contains the required details. There several strategies of pastoral counselling adopted by the church. These strategies are:

- 1. Face-to-Face:** This method affords the unit to meet personally with a counsellor and have a therapeutic session where the counselee enjoys maximum privacy for whatever issues discussed. The counsellors are well-trained to keep matters discussed away from the public. For family issues, in cases where both parties are members, sometimes each party is scheduled for a personal session before inviting both parties for group counselling.
- 2. Special visitations:** Another method embarked on by the team for effective counselling is through visitation. This is usually done by persistently visiting members of the church to know about their welfare and engage them in discussions about the scriptures, life and pray for them.

3. Special Seminars/programs for families: The inclusion of special programmes dedicated to questions on family issues is evident in the church. This is usually accompanied with rigorous prayers. The church is also observing a seven-month family concert seminar especially during Sunday school sessions and sometimes in the main service. There is also a prayer retreat between 9:00 am and 12:00 pm of every Mondays for families (Pastor Ogunleye, personal communication, September 17, 2023)

Impact of Pastoral Counselling in Christ Apostolic Church Oke-Anu

There are several traceable impacts of pastoral counselling on individuals, families and the church. The interviewees are Pastor D. O. Ajaiyeoba (DCC Pastor), Pastor T. O. Ogunleye (Curate Pastor and Counselling Head), and Elder Jaiyeola Victor (Choir Master) who are key members of the church with relevant information that aided the study. From the interviewees in C.A.C Oke-Anu the impacts of pastoral counselling are not limited to the below:

a. It fosters relationship between individuals, families and the church leaders: Pastoral counselling has assisted the church in relationship building through the establishment of a communication network among members and the pastor. Counselling has disclosed several issues which were initially concealed and that have the potential to cause damages to the family.

b. Restoration of broken homes: C.A.C. Oke-Anu has been able to intervene and mend shattered homes and some nearly collapsing relationships through successful counselling. According to Pastor Ogunleye (personal communication, September 17, 2023) there are several cases where members come back to testify how their homes that have been hot and almost scattering have been restored to their first love”.

c. It aids the spiritual growth of the church: On the other hand, pastoral counselling has thus far helped the church to preserve the high spirituality for which it is renowned. Counselling has kept the leaders abreast of the spiritual challenges of the church members and also proffers solutions to them through prayers and divine leading. As a result, the church can claim to have experienced significant spiritual growth and maturity.

d. Increase in Number: Elder Jaiyeola (personal communication, September 17, 2023) submits that effective counselling has added to the number of worshippers and their commitment to the church. Many members and families who happen to be satisfied with the counselling aspect of the church and those regular follow-up services give back total commitment and dedication to the church. To him “it has really encouraged a high number of attendance and dedication to the church more especially during hard and discouraging times like this”.

e. Unity within homes and the church: Many houses have experienced the establishment of true love, peace, and unity through fervent counselling and prayers, which has become a significant reflection inside the church of God. According to Pastor Ogunleye (personal communication, September 17, 2023) when the home is settled in peace and love, the church would match forward in progress and faith.

f. Progress from all spheres: Adequate counselling has fostered progress from all spheres within and outside the church. It was discovered that pastoral counselling has impacted the spiritual progress of all committed and dedicated members, to the fatherly advice for the youths

on chosen fields, to the effective maintenance of a balanced life of a believer (Rom. 12:11; not slothful in business, fervent in Spirit and serving the Lord).

h. Changes from Luke-warmness: Pastor Ogunleye (personal communication, September 17, 2023) confirms that not all humans are the same, neither do people enjoy same upbringing, there have been some members who had initially had negative thoughts about life and have thus reflected such in their relationship with others” pastoral counselling has been cognizant so far in making positive changes in view of such people and have created a better environment for them. These positive changes have really brought out great potentials in such people.

Conclusion

The impacts of pastoral counselling in C.A.C Oke-Anu cannot be overemphasized. Pastoral counsellors often incorporate modern psychological thought and method with traditional religious training in a determination to address psycho-spiritual issues in addition to the traditional spectrum of counselling services (Stephanie, Douglas, & Donna, 2005). It is noted that pastoral counselling in Christ Apostolic Church Oke-Anu serves as a therapeutic measure to physical and spiritual laxity thereby facilitating cure to family related issues within the ambit of the church. The Pastor, Elders and the counselling unit of the church have been of great help in balancing spiritual and physical issues to maintain peace, promote love and restore broken homes within the church. It is therefore safe to say that, counselling is a measure that is needed to be embraced by sundry of Christian denominations in the 21st-century Nigerian society to enhance the level of Church growth and development not only through “prayers” but also through the effective use of the talk therapy.

Recommendations

1. Pastoral counselling should be embraced by all pastors and also pastors should be well-informed and trained about ethics of counselling.
2. Trainings such as seminars, workshops and conferences should be organised for pastoral counsellors to ensure they are up-to-date with the latest counselling techniques and theological insights.
3. Church foster relationship with specialise health institutions or workers to provide therapy for those who require special treatment.
4. Pastoral counselling should be included in outreach endeavours to further extend it beyond the church scope and to enhance evangelism method.
5. It is not enough to have Pastoral counsellor if there is no proper funding and emotional support from the church. Pastoral counsellors should be encouraged with financial resources and emotional support.

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